

Direct determination of impurities in arsenic by atomic spectrometry

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Manuscript received 22 December 2005, accepted 29 March 2006

Abstract : The present paper describes development of Inductively Coupled Plasma-Atomic Emission Spectrometry (ICP-AES) and Electrothermal Atomization-Atomic Absorption Spectrometry (ETA-AAS) for the direct determination of fifteen common metallic and semi-conducting elements in high purity arsenic without prior separation of the major matrix. With a view to improving determination of Cd in arsenic matrix and for providing independent check on determination of few representative elements such as Cu, Cr, Mn and Ni by ICP-AES method, ETA-AAS technique also has been developed for direct determination of these elements in arsenic matrix. A number of synthetic samples have been prepared and analysed by both the techniques to validate the analytical procedures adopted here.

Keywords : ICP-AES, ETA-AAS, arsenic matrix, metallic impurities.

Semiconductors, comprising of elements of group III and group V of the periodic table such as As, Sb, In and Ga find extensive applications in the preparation of electronic and opto-electronic materials^{1,2}. High purity arsenic is a primary starting material for the synthesis of gallium arsenide and indium arsenide. These substances, due to their intrinsic properties, find wide variety of applications in laser diodes, photovoltaic cells, semi-insulating insulators etc. Gallium arsenide (GaAs) in particular forms an integral part of discrete microwave devices, lasers, light emitting diodes, photoelectric cells etc. Further, AsH₃ gas is also used as a dopant in the production of semiconductors. In semiconductor technology, controlled addition of impurities is of crucial importance. An essential part of manufacturing process of semiconductors, therefore, is to check the purity of base materials, intermediaries and final product. Producers of electronic materials are striving hard for high purity constituent materials and finished products. A precise quantitative knowledge of the impurities in such materials is therefore, very essential. The chemical identity, concentration, spatial distribution and lattice position of each type of impurity are important parameters in the preparation of semiconductor materials; hence, for most applications, the synthesis of the material is based on availability of the constituent elements with atleast 5-6 N purity. Due to extreme toxicity of As, the analysis of arsenic is carried out with due care as is observed for analysis of radioactive materials. Several methods such as neutron activation analysis, a

combination of flow-injection analysis and hydride-generation atomic absorption spectroscopy are reported in literature³ to be very sensitive, precise, and accurate methods for determination of arsenic; however, very few reports refer to determination of impurities at trace levels in arsenic samples. Spark Source Mass Spectrometry (SSMS) and Glow Discharge Mass Spectrometry (GDMS) known for their multi-element capability, are explored for the direct analysis of many semi-conducting materials. These techniques, though highly successful in the analysis of conducting metals, when applied to metalloids and non-metals like As, the discharge is very unstable due to rapid loss on evaporation/sputtering of the sample. Liu *et al.*⁴ have described the direct analysis of As by SSMS with limitations of low sensitivity and blackening of the entire spectrum due to mainly non-focused particles. The determination of impurities in arsenic is reported in the past⁵ by D.C. arc emission spectroscopy. Shehervakova *et al.*⁶ had used a specially designed chamber to distill out arsenic as arsenic oxide and residue was dissolved in HCl in the presence of NaCl followed by the determination of impurities. Trace elements in arsenic have also been estimated after separation of the arsenic matrix by volatilization as chloride or bromide in an open system⁷. Udhas *et al.*⁸ have adopted Graphite Furnace-Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (GF-AAS) for the determination of trace and ultra trace impurities in arsenic by *in situ* removal of arsenic matrix in the furnace using an appropriate volatilization step prior to the atomization

stage. Balramakrishna and Arunachalam⁹ have determined trace elements in high purity arsenic through vapour phase dissolution followed by ICP-MS wherein ion exchange and volatilisation methodologies were employed for the quantitative separation of arsenic; however, elements such as Fe, Mg, Zn and Se could not be determined by that method as reported by authors. The authors, in-turn, employed an ICP-AES technique to determine these impurities including the semi conducting elements.

In the present paper, we report the direct determination of elements viz. Al, B, Ca, Cd, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mg, Mn, Ni and Zn along with a few semi conducting elements such as Te, Bi, Se, and Sb by ICP-AES method using an axial viewing ICP excitation source. The paper also describes the application of ETA-AAS for direct determination of Cd, Cu, Cr, Mn and Ni in arsenic matrix. AAS being essentially a single element technique, the analysis was restricted to a few representative elements to provide an in-house independent check on ICP-AES analysis and also validate the procedures adopted.

Table 1. Instrumental details of ICP-AES

Spectrometer model	1M Jobin-Yvon 50-Panorama
Radiofrequency	40 68 (MHz)
RF Power :	
Forward power	1 0 (KW)
Reflected power	< 20 (W)
Type of grating	Holographic
Ruling	3600 (grooves/mm)
Resolution	0 028 (theoretical) (nm)
Slit width	20 (μ m)
Slit height	4 (mm)
Plasma torch position	Horizontal
Viewing position	Axial viewing
Spectral range	165–425 (nm)
Argon gas flow rates :	
Coolant flow	16 (l/min)
Plasma flow	0 (l/min)
Sample flow	1.1 (l/min)
Signal integration time	10 (s)

Results and discussion

AES analysis : The amount of arsenic in the synthetic samples was found to be between 950 to 980 μ g/ml using ICP-AES methods. The detection limits for all the analytes were found to be in the range 0.01–0.05 μ g/ml based on the established criteria of concentration equivalent to blank plus three times the standard deviation in blank measure-

ments for ICP-AES. The data obtained for the synthetic samples on applying a suitable blank correction for the 15 analytes are shown in Table 2. The recoveries of the analytes were found to be quantitative.

AAS analysis : ETA-AAS is well known for its high atomization efficiency. The atom population in ETA-AAS is however, affected by various factors as studied by the authors in the laboratory¹⁰⁻¹³. Therefore, the effect of varying amount of arsenic in the range 0–20 mg/ml on the analyte absorbance was studied using ETA-AAS at 0.02 μ g/ml of Cd concentration. Though arsenic is highly volatile, its presence affects the analyte signal mainly due to the formation of fumes, evolved during atomization stage. Pre-atomization stage was studied to overcome this problem. At high pre-atomization temperatures, the analytes especially Cd suffered a pre-atomization loss. At low pre-atomization temperature, losses could be prevented, however, the removal of large amount of matrix was then found to be difficult. Fumes generated during atomization stage caused physical obstruction to the light path and resulted in absorbance values not related to analyte absorbance signals. The present studies were, therefore, aimed at reducing significantly problems of evaluation of fumes and pre-atomization loss of the analytes. The non-specific absorbance signal was evaluated by using the background correction facility of deuterium lamp continuum source, which, in the present case, could be successfully applied due to high sampling frequency associated with the lamp operation. The heating program was examined carefully by varying the temperature, ramp time and hold time at every stage of heating cycle. The initial three steps in heating cycle belonged essentially to the desolvation stage. The fourth step parameters were varied systematically to ensure minimum evolution of fumes during atomization stage.

The pre-atomization stage for removal of matrix fumes was optimized at 400 °C with a ramp time of 0.1 s from 300 to 400 °C and with hold time of 50 s. The arsenic concentration was optimized to 1 mg/ml for further studies. The absorbance signal at 400 °C due to presence of 1 mg/ml As at the respective analytical lines of interest was found to be insignificant. The heating program optimized for each of the five analytes is given in Table 3. It can be seen from the table that memory effect due to Cr and Ni could be removed effectively by introducing an additional heating step at 2800 °C following the atomization stage.

It was also essential to ensure that the volatilization of the matrix did not accompany loss of analytes. A syn-

Table 2. Results of ICP-AES analysis of synthetic samples

Element	Wave-length (nm)	Sample 1		Sample 2	
		Amount		Amount	
		added ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	determined ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	added ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	determined ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
Al	308.2	0.5	0.51	1.0	1.03
B	249.7	0.1	0.095	0.2	0.18
Ca	396.8	0.5	0.53	1.0	1.01
Cd ^a	214.4	0.1	0.12	0.2	0.21
Cr	205.5	0.1	0.11	0.2	0.21
Cu	324.7	0.1	0.12	0.2	0.20
Fe	259.9	0.1	0.091	0.2	0.20
Mg	285.2	0.1	0.11	0.2	0.19
Mn	257.6	0.05	0.051	0.1	0.12
Ni	232.0	0.25	0.25	0.5	0.48
Zn	213.8	0.1	0.11	0.2	0.20
Bi ^a	227.6	1.0	1.10	2.0	1.90
Se ^a	203.9	1.0	0.90	2.0	1.85
Te ^a	238.5	1.0	0.85	2.0	1.90
Sb ^a	206.8	1.0	1.08	2.0	1.96

^aPolyscan lines were used for estimation.

Table 3. Thermal parameters for Cd, Co, Cr, Mn and Ni in GF-AAS

Heating program steps	Cd			Cr and Ni			Cu and Mn		
	Temp. (°C)	Time (s)		Temp. (°C)	Time (s)		Temp. (°C)	Time (s)	
		Ramp	Hold		Ramp	Hold		Ramp	Hold
1	80	10.0	5.0	80	10.0	6.0	80	10.0	5.0
2	120	10.0	10.0	120	12.0	5.0	120	10.0	10.0
3	300	2.0	2.0	300	3.0	2.0	300	2.0	2.0
4	400	0.1	50	400	0.1	50	400	0.1	50
5	2200	0.9	0.2	2600	1.1	0.3	2400	1.0	0.2
6	-	-	-	2800	0.1	0.2	-	-	-

thetic sample prepared with intermediate range concentration of these analytes and analysed using the optimized procedure showed good agreement between the added contents and the analyte amounts determined. This way, significant removal of matrix interference could be achieved thereby maintaining the analyte signals for all the elements. The effect of the presence of matrix could however, be seen during the studies carried out to determine temperatures for the signal appearance (T_{app}). These temperatures are higher than those observed for non-matrix containing analyte solutions¹⁴. The release of analyte atoms from the residual arsenic matrix within the graphite furnace, thus, appears to be a difficult process and possible only at higher temperatures. The T_{app} values for all the analytes in the presence and absence of arsenic

matrix are shown in Table 4. Udhas *et al.*⁸ have reported determination of impurities in arsenic matrix at As concentration 20 mg/ml. Authors have recommended ashing temperature lower than 300–400 °C for Cd, Bi and Sb but with incomplete volatilization of arsenic and a very strong background signal during atomization stage. They have also reported that it was possible to volatilize arsenic at 600 °C for these elements. However, our studies have shown that 400 °C is the optimum temperature that can be chosen taking into account the analyte losses specially for Cd. This observation is also consistent with the appearance temperature reported by Sturgeon and Chakraborty¹⁴ for Cd in aqueous solution.

Since same atomizer is being used repeatedly for many atomization cycles and arsenic accumulates on each cycle

Table 4. Analytical data for ETA-AAS determination of Cd, Cu, Cr, Mn and Ni in arsenic matrix

Element	Wavelength (nm)	T_{app} (K)		Range of analysis ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Lowest limit of quantitative determination (g)
		Aqu ¹⁴	As		
Cd	228.8	720	850	0.002-0.05	1×10^{-11}
Cu	324.8	1270	1350	0.002-0.04	1×10^{-11}
Cr	425.4	1660	1780	0.01-0.5	5×10^{-11}
Mn	403.1	1480	1510	0.005-0.2	2.5×10^{-11}
Ni	232.0	1590	1690	0.01-0.5	5×10^{-11}

Table 5. Results of synthetic sam pie analysis obtained by ICP-AES and GF-AAS methods

Element	Sample 1 (0.05 $\mu\text{g/ml}$)		Sample 2 (0.2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$)	
	Amount determined		Amount determined	
	ICP-AES	GF-AAS	ICP-AES	GF-AAS
Cd	0.052	0.049	0.22	0.22
Cu	0.051	0.052	0.20	0.21
Cr	0.051	0.052	0.21	0.20
Mn	0.051	0.050	0.24	0.21
Ni	0.049	0.049	0.21	0.19

in the atomizer, the effect of any residual arsenic buildup within the atomizer on the analyte absorbance was also investigated. With 5 μl aliquot containing 5 μg arsenic loaded on the atomizer, analytical signal was found to be unaffected when studied for around 200 atomization cycles. Details of the range of analysis and the smallest amount of the analytes determined directly in arsenic matrix are given in Table 4. The precision of determinations was found to be better than 8% RSD.

GF-AAS is an established technique known for its high sensitivity and very good precision even at ppb levels of detection on chemical separation of the major matrix. Thus it is of great significance to note that the present study involves determination in presence of 1 mg/ml As matrix. Table 5 provides the results of analyses of synthetic samples obtained by both ICP-AES and ETA-AAS techniques which were found to be in good agreement with their spiked concentrations thereby confirming the validation of the present methods.

Experimental

Apparatus :

A Jobin-Yvon (JY-50P) spectrometer equipped with an axial viewing ICP as the excitation source and operated at 40.68 MHz was used for the ICP-AES studies. This instrument known as "Panorama" model, has a unique facility for simultaneous and sequential operation in the same spectrometer assembly enabling determination of 35 elements with a polychromator and a poly scan faci-

lity (JY-50) for unprogrammed elements. The details of the instrument are given in Table 1.

A GBC 906 Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (AAS) with GF-3000 electrothermal atomizer of GBC (Australia) was used. A deuterium lamp was provided for the background correction with a sampling frequency of 200 Hz. The GF power supply provided step-wise heating programme (10 steps) with heating rate as high as 2000 $^{\circ}\text{C/s}$ to graphite tube atomizer. Argon was used as sheath gas and the absorbance signal was measured in the peak height mode. An Eppendorff fixed volume pipette (5 μl) was used for dispensing sample/standard aliquot into the graphite furnace, while Eppendorff variable volume pipette was used in the preparation of standard/sample solutions. Arsenic fumes being highly toxic, adequate exhaust system was provided around the atomizer.

Reagents :

All the reagents like HNO_3 , HCl used in these studies were of electronic grade. Quartz double-distilled water was used for preparation of all standard solutions, reagent blank etc.

Preparation of standards :

AES analysis : The arsenic nitrate solutions was prepared by dissolving 200 mg of high purity arsenic oxide in concentrated HNO_3 with the addition of 100 μl of concentrated HCl. HCl was removed by repeated addition of concentrated HNO_3 and heating the solution to near dryness under IR lamp. The solution was finally

made up to 10 ml in 1.0 M HNO₃. A 20 ppm As standard was prepared from this stock to monitor As interference on analyte channels.

Stock solutions of the impurity elements of interest (5 mg/ml) were prepared using spec pure oxides (Johnson Matthey, UK) of the respective elements. Appropriate aliquots of these elemental stock solutions were mixed together to make a multi element standard (20 µg/ml) in 1 M HNO₃ medium. 1 M HNO₃ solution served as the low standard for each of the analyte of interest while 20 µg/ml multi-element standard served as the high standard for the two point standardization procedure.

AAS analysis : From the stock solution of As, a set of standard solutions was prepared by adding varying concentrations of arsenic in the range 0–20 mg/ml to a fixed concentration of 0.02 µg/ml of each of Cd, Cu, Cr, Mn and Ni. Zero concentration being arsenic free analyte solution to study the effects of matrix on the analyte absorbance. On detailed studies, arsenic concentration was restricted to 1 mg/ml for AAS studies. A series of standards in the range 0.001–1.0 µg/ml was prepared for Cd, Cu, Cr, Mn and Ni in 1 mg/ml arsenic.

Preparation of synthetic samples :

For ICP-AES studies, two synthetic samples of arsenic were prepared by taking 25 mg of high purity arsenic oxide (As₂O₃) as matrix. To the dissolved solution, known aliquots of the 15 impurity elements including Al, B, Ca, Cd, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mg, Mn, Ni and Zn and a few semi conducting elements such as Te, Bi, Se, and Sb were added at different levels ranging from 0.05 µg/ml to 2.0 µg/ml. The solution was finally made up to 25 ml in 1 M HNO₃, thereby maintaining the arsenic concentration at 1 mg/ml. One sample at 1 mg/ml of high purity As was also prepared in the same way but without the addition of any of the analyte elements. This sample served as the blank to account for any contribution from the matrix to the analyte channels during the ICP-AES studies. These samples were subsequently employed for ICP-AES analysis for determination of the analytes of interest. In addition two more samples were prepared with the addition of a few representative elements viz. Cd, Cu, Cr, Mn and Ni at 0.05 and 0.2 µg/ml respectively and were analysed by both ICP-AES and ETA-AAS methods.

Procedure :

AES analysis : The synthetic samples of arsenic (1 mg/ml) were aspirated through a concentric nebuliser to the plasma torch with axial viewing facility for optimization of relevant experimental parameters. A calibration curve was obtained during the two-point standardization carried out using 1 M HNO₃ as the lower standard and 20 ppm standard as the higher standard. For Sb, Te, Bi, Se and As suitable poly scan lines were chosen taking into account the probable interference from the matrix lines.

The polychromator line of Cd (228.802 nm) was found to have a spectral interference with that of arsenic line (228.812 nm), which necessitated the use of a suitable polyscan line for Cd (214.4 nm). An arsenic line at 189.042 nm was also monitored simultaneously in all the samples.

AAS analysis : A 5 µl aliquot of sample/standard solution was injected into graphite furnace and a six-step furnace heating parameters were standardized for all analytes with arsenic matrix and calibration curves and other analytical data were obtained. In order to remove memory effect for Cr and Ni, an additional step for tube cleaning at 2800 °C was also introduced. The effect of matrix accumulation inside the atomizer on the analyte absorbance was also studied for each of the analyte.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. V. K. Manchanda, Head, Radiochemistry Division, BARC, Mumbai, for his keen interest and encouragement during the course of this work.

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